

TransformAr

Accelerating and upscaling transformational adaptation in
Europe: demonstration of water-related innovation
packages

Report on willingness to pay for solutions

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents the results of a discrete choice experiment (DCE) exploring citizens' willingness to pay (WTP) for stormwater management (SWM) measures in Finland and Norway. The study is situated within the TransformAr project, which accelerates climate adaptation through innovative, demand-driven solutions. Climate change is intensifying rainfall events, flooding, and runoff pollution across Northern Europe, putting pressure on urban drainage systems. Effective adaptation therefore requires not only public investment but also citizen engagement and household-level contributions.

A nationally representative survey of 2,013 respondents (1,013 in Finland and 1,000 in Norway) assessed preferences across five attributes: reduced risk of damage to the house, reduced stormwater runoff and pollution, improved aesthetics of the property and community, frequency of maintenance required and price (investment cost). Results were analyzed using mixed logit and latent class models to capture both average WTP and preference heterogeneity. To complement the survey, a resident workshop was held in Lappeenranta (Finland) to provide qualitative insights into household-level risks, practical constraints, and adaptation ideas, enriching and contextualizing the survey findings.

Findings show that citizens clearly favored stormwater management solutions that reduce property flood risk and stormwater runoff/pollution, while they were least supportive of options requiring frequent maintenance. Finnish households expressed the highest WTP for property risk reduction, up to €4,820 for a 75% reduction in flood damage. Norwegian households valued runoff and pollution reduction most strongly, with WTP up to €3,550 for a 50% reduction. Aesthetic improvements were positively valued, especially in Finland (€1,257 vs. €615 in Norway). Maintenance requirements emerged as a critical barrier, with bi-monthly upkeep reducing WTP by over €3,500 per household. Socioeconomic factors shaped preferences in meaningful ways. These priorities were echoed in the workshop discussions, where residents also emphasized affordability, practical yard constraints, and the importance of municipal guidance and support.

A stronger propensity to support investment was observed among residents with greater financial means, higher educational attainment, or prior exposure to flooding. In contrast, older respondents demonstrated comparatively lower investment willingness. Homeownership status did not significantly affect preferences, but the market value of respondents' properties was positively associated with support for enhanced measures. These quantitative findings were reinforced by the workshop discussions, where residents emphasized the same priorities: property protection, runoff management, aesthetics, and low-maintenance solutions, while also stressing that affordability and clear guidance are essential for uptake at the household level.

From these insights, six interrelated policy directions are proposed: (1) focus on property and water protection, (2) integrate aesthetic value through green infrastructure, (3) minimize maintenance burdens or provide municipal support, (4) tailor communication and incentives to citizen groups, (5) ensure equitable access through subsidies and progressive financing, and (6) build trust via transparency, pilot projects, and participatory engagement.

Overall, the study demonstrates that citizens in Finland and Norway are not passive beneficiaries but show a clear willingness to act as active partners in climate adaptation. When measures are effective, affordable, and equitable, they are willing to invest in protecting their homes, communities, and environments. Key partners, the City of Lappeenranta in Finland and the Municipality of Gjøvik in Norway, will continue engaging stakeholders and citizens to co-develop stormwater management solutions, ensuring evidence-based, citizen-driven strategies strengthen resilience, foster legitimacy, and accelerate transformational adaptation.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AAS	Actionable Adaptation Solutions
ANA	Attribute-non-attendance
ASC	Alternative Specific Constant
DCE	Discrete Choice Experiment
CEI	Choice Experiment
LID	Low Impact Development
LCM	Latent Class Model
MWTP	Marginal Willingness To Pay
MXL	Mixed logit
SWM	Stormwater Management
WTP	Willingness To Pay

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

This report is prepared as part of the TransformAr project, which aims to accelerate climate adaptation through transformative solutions that strengthen systemic resilience across Europe. TransformAr supports the design, testing, and scaling of Actionable Adaptation Solutions (AAS) across multiple demonstrator regions. Within the TransformAr solution framework, this study contributes to the Insurance, Financial and Economic Instruments (IFE) category¹. The discrete choice experiment (DCE)² presented in this report is recognised as one such solution: a policy-support and economic tool to reveal citizens' willingness to pay (WTP) for flood risk reduction and other benefits associated with stormwater management (SWM). By understanding the economic value that citizens place on different SWM attributes, the DCE helps guide the development of inclusive, demand-driven, and cost-effective adaptation pathways.

Climate change is increasingly recognized as one of the most pressing challenges for urban areas in Northern Europe. In both Finland and Norway, shifts in precipitation patterns and warmer winters are leading to more frequent and intense rainfall events, rapid snowmelt, and subsequent urban flooding (Haveraaen, 2024; Wang et al., 2022). These changes place substantial pressure on stormwater and drainage networks that were not originally designed to handle such extreme conditions. The consequences include damage to private property, risks to public safety, and deterioration in water quality due to increased runoff and pollution (Wang et al., 2022).

Stormwater management (SWM) is a critical adaptation measure to address these risks. Traditionally, SWM has relied heavily on "grey infrastructure," such as underground pipes, chambers, and sump pumps (Furuset al., 2018). While effective in many cases, grey solutions are costly, inflexible, and often limited in addressing the broader ecological and social dimensions of flood risk (EEA, 2016). In recent years, "green infrastructure" approaches have gained traction. These include permeable pavements, rain gardens, green roofs, and wetlands, which not only manage water flow but also provide co-benefits such as biodiversity support, improved urban aesthetics, and enhanced community well-being (Johnson & Geisendorf, 2022).

Despite these benefits, adoption of SWM measures on private properties remains uneven. Many cities rely primarily on public investment, leaving household-level contributions underutilized. Yet, private properties account for a significant proportion of urban surface area, and their role in stormwater management is increasingly critical. Understanding the willingness of citizens to adopt and financially support SWM measures can therefore significantly enhance overall resilience to flooding.

This report is based on a discrete choice experiment (DCE) conducted with more than 2,000 residents across Finland and Norway. The study provides fresh evidence on citizens' preferences for SWM attributes, including risk reduction, runoff control, aesthetic improvements, maintenance requirements, and costs. By translating these findings into practical guidance, the report aims to support municipalities, urban planners, and policymakers in designing solutions that reflect public priorities while achieving climate resilience goals.

¹ There are five solution categories in TransformAR: Behavioural change and awareness-raising (BCAR), Governance Schemes (GS), Nature-Based Solutions (NBS), Technological and Digital Solutions (TDS), and Insurance, financial and economic schemes (IFE).

² Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE) may also be referred to as Choice Experiment (CE) in other contexts or deliverables within the TransformAr project.

1.2 Local context

In Finland, cities around the coastal areas are particularly affected by flooding risk resulting from snowmelt and winter rainfall. The flood risk map by the Finnish Environment Institute identifies key flood-prone areas in several coastal and urban regions (Syke, 2024), Figure 1.a). These zones represent urban centers where existing infrastructure struggles to cope with extreme weather. Norway faces similar vulnerabilities due to steep terrain and increasing precipitation intensity. According to flood risk maps by the Norwegian Water Resources and Energy Directorate (NVE, 2024), Figure 1.b), coastal cities are particularly exposed, with flash floods exacerbated by topographical runoff.

In both countries, flood risks are influenced by climate-related drivers such as snowmelt and rising water levels, as well as human activities including land use changes, drainage system limitations, and water control structures. Storm Hans, which hit the region in August 2023, highlighted these challenges as many residents faced flooding due to overwhelmed stormwater networks. In addition to property damage, these events contribute to lake pollution, eutrophication, and broader threats to ecosystem and public health (Haveraaen, 2024). According to the Norwegian Institute’s survey, 78% of respondents reported using Low Impact Development (LID) techniques such as underground retention tanks, rain gardens, permeable surfaces, and green roofs (Furuset et al., 2018). Traditional grey infrastructure—levelling land, pumps, and flood-proofing measures—remains widely used. Given the mix of approaches in practice, this study fills an important research gap by comparing how citizens in both countries evaluate green and grey SWM solutions.

Figure 1.1 Flooding risk map of a) Finland (Syke, 2024) (Red: Significant flood risk areas; Orange: potential flood-prone areas) b) Norway—Areas (blue points) happened flooding by extreme weather (Norwegian Water Resources and Energy Directorate, 2024)

1.3 Objectives and Scope

The overarching goal of this report is to present evidence on how citizens in Finland and Norway value different stormwater management strategies, and the extent to which they are willing to invest in such solutions to reduce climate-related risks. More specifically, the report pursues the following objectives:

1. Assess citizens’ public acceptance and willingness to pay (WTP)
 - Estimate the financial contributions residents are prepared to make for different SWM measures.
 - Compare variations between Finland and Norway to understand country-specific preferences.

2. Identify key attributes shaping decision-making

- Determine the relative importance of risk reduction, runoff reduction, aesthetics, maintenance requirements, and investment cost.
- Highlight which combinations of attributes are most attractive to households.

3. Analyze heterogeneity of preferences

- Investigate how demographic and socioeconomic characteristics (such as age, income, education, and flood experience) influence willingness to pay and preferences.
- Use latent class modeling to identify distinct groups of citizens with similar patterns of preferences.

4. Provide actionable recommendations

- Translate findings into practical strategies for municipalities and policymakers.
- Suggest incentive mechanisms (e.g., subsidies, tax deductions, or maintenance support) to enhance citizen participation.

In addition to the national survey, complementary qualitative evidence was collected through a resident workshop in Lappeenranta, Finland. This workshop focused on detached housing and yard-level adaptation, providing practical perspectives that enrich and contextualise the survey-based results.

The scope of the report is deliberately practical. While the associated academic publication emphasizes the methodological contributions and theoretical significance of the DCE, this report focuses on the applied relevance of the findings. The emphasis is on informing decision-makers about how to better design, fund, and promote stormwater management measures that align with the needs and priorities of residents.

The geographic scope includes both Finland and Norway, with national-level surveys ensuring broad coverage. While the results provide valuable insights for these two countries, the methodology and findings may also be relevant for other regions experiencing similar urban flooding challenges.

1.4 Target Audiences

This report is designed for a broad range of stakeholders involved in climate adaptation, urban planning, and environmental management. The key target audiences include:

- **Policymakers and Municipal Authorities:** Municipalities play a central role in designing and funding stormwater infrastructure. For them, the report offers practical evidence on how local residents perceive different SWM strategies and how much they are willing to contribute financially. Understanding these preferences allows municipalities to design policies that are both technically effective and socially acceptable. For example, if maintenance requirements are shown to reduce citizen support, municipalities may consider offering maintenance services or cost-sharing arrangements.
- **Urban Planners and Engineers:** Urban planners, architects, and infrastructure engineers are responsible for developing and implementing stormwater solutions that integrate into the built environment. This report provides insights into which features (e.g., permeable surfaces, rain gardens, or grey solutions like sump pumps) are most valued by citizens, helping professionals design interventions that are not only functional but also well-received by the public.
- **National Government Agencies:** National-level agencies responsible for climate adaptation, water management, and environmental protection can use the findings to align local initiatives with broader policy frameworks. By understanding citizens' willingness to pay, governments can

better design national programs that complement local efforts and ensure consistent adaptation strategies across regions.

- **Community Organizations and NGOs:** Environmental organizations, neighborhood associations, and advocacy groups working on climate resilience and sustainable urban living can benefit from the report's evidence. The findings can strengthen advocacy campaigns, support educational efforts, and help communities push for more citizen-friendly policies on stormwater management.
- **Resident Associations and Community Groups:** Local organizations and neighborhood-level groups can benefit from the findings by using them to raise awareness, develop practical adaptation ideas, and strengthen the connection between municipal policies and household-level action.
- **Academic and Research Communities:** Although the primary emphasis of the report is practical, researchers studying climate adaptation, environmental economics, and urban sustainability will find value in methodological transparency and the application of the discrete choice experiment approach in a Nordic context. The report complements the academic article by offering a more practice-oriented perspective on the same data.

In summary, this report bridges the gap between academic research and policy application. It presents robust evidence on citizens' preferences for stormwater management measures in Finland and Norway, translating complex econometric findings into clear guidance for decision-makers. By highlighting what residents value most and what discourages their participation, the report supports the design of strategies that are equitable, effective, and aligned with public priorities. Ultimately, the findings demonstrate that citizens are not passive observers in the face of climate change but active partners willing to invest in solutions that protect their homes, communities, and environments. Ensuring their voices are incorporated into decision-making is essential for building resilient and sustainable urban futures.

2.0 METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

This section describes the methodological approach used to assess citizens' willingness to pay (WTP) for stormwater management (SWM) solutions in Finland and Norway. The core method was a Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE), a survey-based technique that presents respondents with hypothetical yet realistic scenarios to capture their preferences and trade-offs. To complement the survey, a resident workshop in Lappeenranta (Finland) gathered qualitative insights on climate risks, yard-level practices, and support needs, enriching and triangulating the survey findings.

2.1 Discrete Choice Experiment

SWM is a complex policy challenge where multiple solutions with varying costs, benefits, and trade-offs are available. Traditional survey methods often fail to capture how people value multiple attributes simultaneously. Stated preference methods, including contingent valuation and discrete choice experiments (DCE), have been widely used in environmental economics to assess values for non-market goods (Hanley & Barbier, 2009; Alriksson & Öberg, 2008; Cadavid, 2013). Stated preference approaches are particularly relevant where market data are absent, allowing preferences for hypothetical but realistic scenarios to be elicited.

The DCE approach was selected because:

- It allows respondents to express preferences across multiple attributes instead of evaluating measures in isolation.
- It reveals the trade-offs citizens are willing to make between benefits such as flood risk reduction and costs such as maintenance or investment.
- It enables the calculation of monetary values (WTP) for different improvements, which can directly inform policy and cost–benefit analysis.

Compared to contingent valuation, which elicits willingness to pay for a single outcome, DCEs provide richer information on how individuals make choices among alternatives. The approach has been widely applied in environmental economics and policy design, especially for valuing non-market goods such as ecosystem services and climate adaptation measures.

2.2 Choice Scenarios

In our study, respondents were presented with a series of hypothetical SWM options to evaluate. Each choice set included two different SWM solutions and one opt-out alternative (choosing not to implement any new measure). Every option was described using a set of defined attributes such as effectiveness, aesthetics, maintenance frequency, and cost, to ensure clarity and avoid confusion or knowledge bias (Bjørnåvold et al., 2020; Mariel et al., 2021). To encourage realistic responses, a cost attribute was included in each option. This follows the principles of incentive compatibility (Mariel et al., 2021), where the inclusion of realistic monetary values prompts respondents to treat the decision as if they were making an actual investment. The design of the DCE was intended to reflect real-world trade-offs and ensure that respondents' choices represented their true preferences and willingness to support SWM measures.

The choice scenarios (or cards) were created using a D-efficient design in Ngene software. Each card featured three alternatives: two new hypothetical SWM options and a status quo (opt-out) option. The attribute levels for each scenario were systematically varied, and the resulting cards were divided into three blocks. Each respondent was randomly assigned one block and completed six choice tasks accordingly.

The design of the DCE required the careful selection of attributes and levels that realistically reflect the decisions households may face when considering SWM measures. Attributes were identified through a review of academic literature, consultations with experts and local authorities in Finland and Norway, and pilot tests conducted in Lappeenranta and Gjøvik. The goal was to capture both the direct benefits of SWM, such as flood risk reduction, and the co-benefits and trade-offs, such as aesthetics, maintenance requirements, and financial costs.

Five attributes are selected: 1) Reduced risk of damage to the house; 2) Reduced stormwater runoff and pollution; 3) Improved aesthetics of the property and community; 4) Frequency of maintenance required and 5) Price (Investment cost). Each attribute was described using clearly defined levels that provided realistic variation without overwhelming respondents. These levels were designed to reflect the range of outcomes that municipalities or households might realistically encounter. Table 2.1 provides an overview of the selected attributes and their levels.

Table 2.1 Attributes and levels

		<u>Definition</u>	<u>Levels to choose from</u>
	Reduced risk of damage to the house	By installing effective stormwater management measures on your property, you reduce the risk of flooding and minimise potential damage caused by excessive rainfall compared to what may occur in its present condition.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 75 % less risk of damage - 50 % less risk of damage - 25 % less risk of damage No reduction in risk of damage (same as now)
	Reduced stormwater run-off and pollution	Stormwater runoff is the water that flows over the surface when it rains or when snow and ice melt. Instead of soaking into the ground, this water runs off over streets, parking lots, and rooftops, picking up pollutants (like oil, chemicals, sediments and debris). Effective stormwater management will reduce the stormwater runoff from your property, including pollutants, flowing into local water bodies, thus ensuring local water quality.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 75 % less run-off pollutants - 50 % less run-off pollutants - 25 % less run-off pollutants No reduction in run-off pollutants (same as now)
	Improved aesthetics of the property and community	The stormwater measure can beautify your property and the local community (or not).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Yes No (same as now)
	Frequency of maintenance required	The frequency at which you will have to take action to maintain the stormwater management measure.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Once every 2 months Once every 6 months Once a year Once every 2 years
	Price (investment cost)	The price to pay to install the stormwater management measure on your property.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 100 000 KR/10 000 EUR 40 000 KR/4 000 EUR 10 000 KR/1 000 EUR 5000 KR/500 EUR

Respondents were asked to evaluate choice cards, each presenting two alternative SWM strategies and one “status quo” option (no action). This design ensured that respondents could opt out if they preferred not to invest, which reduces bias and provides more realistic results. An example of a choice card is shown below in Table 2.2.

Table 2.2 Example of a choice card

	Reduced risk of damage to the house	Reduced stormwater run-off and pollution	Improvement of aesthetics of the property and community	Frequency of maintenance required	Price (investment cost)
A	 € 1000				
B	 € 500				
C	No new stormwater management measure				

2.3 Survey Design

The questionnaire consisted of six sections (see details in Annex 1). The first section collected contextual information about the respondents' properties. This included details such as housing tenure (owned or rented), the number of people living in the household, the presence of a garden, proximity to green spaces, the market value of the property (for homeowners), and the year the property was built. The second section focused on respondents' perceptions of climate change impacts within their local area. This section aimed to capture how individuals perceive the effects of changing weather patterns and environmental risks in their communities, which may influence their preferences and decisions regarding stormwater management solutions.

In the third section, participants were asked about their experience with SWM and any SWM strategies currently in place on their properties. The survey was carried out between January and February 2024, reaching 1,013 residents in Finland and 1,000 in Norway. To minimize systematic selection bias, the survey software (Qualtrics) randomly assigned one of the three survey blocks, each containing six standard DCE choice sets, to each respondent. After the questionnaire design was finalized, we conducted a pilot test in two cities, Lappeenranta (Finland) and Gjøvik (Norway), with a small group of citizens. This pilot phase was supported by local authorities and universities to ensure that the questionnaire was clear, relevant, and understandable for residents.

In this section, respondents were informed about climate change and SWM:

“Extreme weather events are occurring more often due to the impacts of climate change. In the event of heavy rainfall, you may experience floods on your property, as the stormwater and drainage network will be overloaded.”

Figure 2.1 Impact of Storm Hans in Norway, August 2023

We further emphasized the importance of citizens acting within their local community and on their property as

“To adapt to these impacts of climate change, and to relieve the water network, it is important that both the government and citizens take action. If stormwater management measures are implemented in your local community and your property, water will naturally go into the ground, and not flow into the drainage network at once. This reduces the risk of flooding, in addition to risks caused by winter rainfall, freezing temperatures and ice covering surfaces on your property, and as a result: a reduced risk of falls, injuries and accidents. Increased stormwater management will also improve water quality as a result of a reduction in run-off pollutants flowing into local water bodies.”

The hypothetical scenario presented to respondents was the following:

"Imagine the following hypothetical scenario: You are considering purchasing one of the below stormwater management measures for your private property to capture increased rainfall and stormwater. You own a detached 120 m² house with a garden. In the following section, we will ask you to choose your preferred stormwater management measures based on their costs and benefits below. You will be asked afterwards which specific measures you had in mind. We will NOT specify the specific measure; however all the options do represent some indirectly. You are also given the option to opt-out of the choice, and not implement a stormwater measure on your property. The prices provided are for a detached 120 m² house with a garden. You will be given the option to choose 6 independent times. There are no right or wrong answers."

Figure 2.2 Stormwater management for private property

The option to select an apartment as a housing type was not included in the survey, as many of the stormwater management (SWM) measures under consideration are not feasible for installation in apartment settings. To ensure informed decision-making, respondents were shown individual slides explaining the key benefits and disadvantages of various SWM strategies (see an example in Figure 2.3).

Green roof & green walls

Benefits	Disadvantages
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce stormwater runoff to prevent flooding and erosion • Filter pollutants out of rainwater and the air to improve local water and air quality • Provide habitat for wildlife • Decrease energy costs • Increase the property value 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expensive to install • Not suitable for all houses • Increase leakage risks • Add weight to the building • Require some maintenance

Figure 2.3 An example of the explanation of stormwater management

The fifth section of the questionnaire served as a post-experimental component aimed at assessing respondents' reflections on DCE. The sixth section collected basic socioeconomic information from respondents. This included variables such as gender, age, level of education, and monthly household

income. These data were used to analyze heterogeneity in preferences and to explore potential correlations between demographic characteristics and WTP for SWM measures.

Following the finalization of the questionnaire design, a pilot test was conducted in two cities: Lappeenranta (Finland) and Gjøvik (Norway). The pilot phase included ten in-depth, face-to-face interviews with citizens from each country. These participants were recruited through the networks of the City of Lappeenranta and the Municipality of Gjøvik. Importantly, not all interviewees were familiar with stormwater management topics, in order to reflect the general population targeted by the survey. The objective of the pilot test was to assess the clarity, relevance, and comprehensibility of both the questionnaire and the choice sets. Interviews were conducted separately in each location by local authorities and university representatives.

After incorporating feedback from the pilot phase, the main survey was distributed between January and February 2024. A professional survey company managed the distribution in both countries. The sample was designed to be nationally representative in terms of age, gender, income, education, and regional distribution. A total of 1,013 responses were collected in Finland and 1,000 in Norway.

2.4 Analytical Approach

The theoretical basis for DCEs is based on Lancaster's Theory of Value (Louviere & Hensher, 1982), which offers a scientific framework for estimating the trade-offs individuals make between multiple attributes that vary concurrently.

To quantify preferences for stormwater management, an econometric model is fitted to the choice data. This model is built on the random utility framework, which posits that the utility a respondent derives from an alternative (U) consists of a deterministic, observable component (V) defined by the alternative's attributes and a random, unobservable component (ϵ).

$$U_{ijt} = V_{ijt} + \epsilon_{ijt}$$

Within this framework, a respondent is assumed to select the alternative that delivers the highest utility. The probability of choosing alternative *j* is therefore the probability that its total utility exceeds that of all other available options. The probability of this choice is shown in the equation below:

$$P_{ijt} = \text{Prob} (U_{ijt} > U_{iht}, \forall h \neq j)$$
$$P_{ijt} = \text{Prob} (V_{ijt} + \epsilon_{iht} > V_{ijt} + \epsilon_{iht}, \forall h \neq j)$$
$$P_{ijt} = \text{Prob} (\epsilon_{ijt} - \epsilon_{iht} > V_{ijt} - V_{iht}, \forall h \neq j)$$

2.4.1 Mixed Logit Model

To analyze resident preferences and the sources of heterogeneity, we employed a Mixed Logit (MXL) model. The key advantage of MXL is its ability to accommodate individual specific tastes by specifying coefficients as random variables following a distribution, rather than as fixed values (Mariel et al., 2021).

The model estimates two key parameters for each attribute: a mean coefficient (β) representing the average preference, and a standard deviation (Δs_i) indicating the spread of preferences around that mean. A statistically significant standard deviation is interpreted as evidence of preference heterogeneity for that attribute.

The choice probability is expressed by a formula where the utility coefficients β_i are a function of the population mean (β), individual heterogeneity (Δs_i), and a stochastic error term (ϵ_i) capturing unmodeled influences (Hensher & Greene, 2003).. The probability that respondent i chooses alternative j in choice t that maximizes its utility as follows:

$$P_{ijt} = \frac{\exp(\beta_i X_{jt})}{\sum_{j=1}^{J_i} \exp(\beta_i X_{jt})}; \beta_i = \beta + \Delta s_i + \varepsilon_i$$

Our models included Alternative-Specific Constants (ASCs) to account for biases or preferences not directly linked to the attributes we listed (Meyerhoff & Liebe, 2009). For example, a positive ASC suggests people inherently support the new stormwater strategies, while a negative one implies inherent opposition.

We also calculated the Marginal Willingness to Pay (WTP) for each attribute. This measures how much more (or less) residents are willing to pay for an improvement in a specific feature. It's calculated by comparing the strength of their preference for that feature to their sensitivity to price.

$$MWTP = \frac{\beta_{\text{attribute level}}}{\beta_{\text{price}}}$$

2.4.2 Latent Class Model

The Latent Class Model (LCM) identifies distinct groups of respondents who share similar preferences. Unlike other models that see a smooth distribution of tastes, the LCM assumes that the population is composed of a few unique segments, each with its own set of values for the attributes (Mariel et al., 2021). After determining these classes, researchers can analyze the demographic or psychographic profiles of each group to understand what characterizes them. The model uses a standard logistic probability formula to calculate the likelihood of a choice within each specific class.

The probability that respondent i selects option j in choice t within a given latent class L is calculated using a formula below based on the concept of utility maximization. The probability formula is given by:

$$P_{ijt|l} = \frac{\exp(\beta_i X_{jt})}{\sum_{j=1}^{J_i} \exp(\beta_i X_{jt})}$$

This formula represents how likely it is that respondent i would choose option j in class L , based on the attributes of the choice (X_{jt}) and the respondent's preference parameters (β_i).

The econometric analysis was conducted in Stata 18. Model estimation utilized 1,000 Halton draws, a quasi-Monte Carlo method that enhances the precision and reliability of parameter estimates by ensuring a more uniform distribution across the potential value space (Train, K.E., 2009).

Preference heterogeneity was captured by specifying all attributes as random parameters, with interaction terms treated as fixed. Furthermore, we integrated a control for attribute non-attendance (ANA) to mitigate the bias introduced when respondents disregard specific attributes (Nguyen et al., 2015). This was implemented by using respondents' self-reported ignored attributes to constrain their corresponding coefficients to zero during estimation. These analyses were run on segregated and pooled datasets to yield a nuanced understanding of SWM preferences in diverse urban contexts.

2.5 Resident Workshop

In addition to the survey-based DCE, complementary qualitative evidence was collected through a resident workshop held in Lappeenranta, Finland, on August 19th, 2025. The workshop was designed and facilitated by a consulting company, in collaboration with the City of Lappeenranta. It built directly on the survey results, particularly the revealed preferences for risk reduction, runoff control, aesthetics, and low-maintenance solutions.

The workshop had three objectives:

- **Increase and share knowledge:** Raise awareness among residents (detached house owners, those building or planning to build) about the local impacts of climate change and share information on the city’s work toward adaptation.
- **Collect information:** Gather residents’ views on climate risk management, especially regarding stormwater, and brainstorm ways to strengthen resilience.
- **Activate participation:** Encourage and inspire participants to take action for climate change adaptation and preparedness, and find out what support they expect from the city.

To set the stage, participants received short expert presentations: “Detached housing in a changing climate: what to prepare for and how?” and “Stormwater management in Lappeenranta”. The workshop was structured to encourage active participation, reflection, and idea generation through a three-part process: **warm-up**, **orientation**, and **activation** (Figure 2.4). In the Warm-up, participants selected their favorite yard from a set of photos (examples in Figure 2.5) and shared their choice with others in their small group, helping to build rapport and highlight personal preferences. During the Orientation phase, the focus shifted to analyzing how climate change might affect the example yards and what consequences those impacts could have. Participants wrote down their thoughts individually before discussing them as a group and noting key points next to the images. The final phase, Activation, encouraged participants to identify practical solutions for climate adaptation, both those shown in the pictures and others they would be interested in trying themselves. They also considered what kind of support they would need from the city to implement these measures. Each group marked their top ideas and prepared to share them with the larger group, setting the stage for shared learning and further action.

Figure 2.4 Workshop process

Figure 2.5 Possible example yards

This participatory format emphasized engagement and co-creation, allowing residents to articulate both priorities and perceived barriers. Data was collected through group notes, facilitator summaries, and reflections captured during discussions. While not designed for statistical generalization, the workshop provided qualitative insights that triangulate and enrich the survey evidence, highlighting practical pathways for aligning municipal support with citizen willingness.

3.0 RESULTS AND FINDINGS

This section presents the main findings from the discrete choice experiment (DCE) conducted among 2,013 citizens in Finland and Norway, and a resident workshop in Lappeenranta (Finland). It provides an overview of the respondents' demographic profiles, their preferences for stormwater management (SWM) strategies, and the heterogeneity of these preferences across different social groups. The analysis draws on both the Mixed Logit (MXL) Model and the Latent Class Model (LCM) to capture not only average preferences but also variations within the population, while the workshop findings provide contextual household-level perspectives on risks, measures, and support needs.

3.1 Survey Respondent Profile

The survey collected 1,013 responses from Finland and 1,000 from Norway. The sample was generally balanced in terms of gender and spanned all major age groups, with the largest proportion (22.11%) being 30-40 years old. The most common monthly household income was €3001–€4500.

Educational attainment and housing type differed between the countries. A higher percentage of Finnish respondents had a secondary education (45.3%), while a lower university degree was more common in Norway (45.6%). Most respondents lived in an apartment (44.31%) or a detached house (37.66%), and 59.17% owned their property. Detailed socio-demographics are presented in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1 Descriptive statistics

Variable (dummies)	Finland (n=1013)	Norway (n=1000)	Total (n=2013)	Percentage of total (%)
<i>Gender</i>				
Female	515	499	1014	50.37
<i>Age</i>				
18-20 years	16	20	36	1.79
20-30 years	182	182	364	18.08
30-40 years	211	234	445	22.11
40-50 years	218	203	421	20.91
50-60 years	201	209	410	20.37
Over 60 years	183	147	330	16.39
<i>Monthly family income</i>				
Less than €1500	215	43	258	12.82
€1501 - €3000	272	90	362	17.98
€3001 - €4500	208	225	433	21.51
€4501 - €6000	118	236	354	17.59
€6001 - €7500	44	134	178	8.84
€7501 - €12500	31	81	112	5.56
more than €12500	6	106	112	5.56
I don't not know	24	18	42	2.09

I do not want to tell	95	67	162	8.05
<i>Education</i>				
Primary school	93	50	143	7.10
Second degree education	459	290	749	37.21
Lower university degree	276	456	732	36.36
Master's degree	177	196	373	18.53
I do not want to tell	8	8	16	0.79
<i>Housing type</i>				
In a detached house	311	447	758	37.66
In a semi-detached house	42	68	110	5.46
In a row house	139	95	234	11.62
In an apartment building	516	376	892	44.31
Elsewhere	5	14	19	0.94
<i>Rented or owned</i>				
Ownership	500	691	1191	59.17
Rental	506	293	799	39.69
I do not want to tell	7	16	23	1.14
<i>Property has been affected by floods</i>				
More than once a year	8	13	21	1.04
Once a year	19	23	42	2.09
Every 1-3 years	19	31	50	2.48
Every 3-5 years	20	39	59	2.93
Every 5-10 years	9	21	30	1.49
Less often than once in 10 years	59	65	124	6.16
Never	694	744	1438	71.44
Another option	0	3	3	0.15
I do not know	185	61	246	12.22
<i>Floods have happened in neighborhood</i>				
More than once a year	24	21	45	2.24
Once a year	62	27	89	4.42
Every 1-3 years	34	62	96	4.77
Every 3-5 years	30	39	69	3.43
Every 5-10 years	26	37	63	3.13
Less often than once in 10 years	79	101	259	12.87
Never	463	601	1064	52.86
Another option	1	3	4	0.20

I do not know	294	109	403	20.02
<i>Regions</i>				
Central	45	89	134	6.66
Northern	117	93	210	10.43
Southern	545	60	605	30.05
Eastern	119	518	637	31.64
Western	263	239	502	24.94

3.2 Results from MXL

The discrete choice experiment (DCE) data were analyzed using Stata 18, with model parameters estimated via 2,000 Halton draws to ensure precision. Attributes including flood risk reduction, runoff reduction, maintenance frequency, and cost were specified as continuous variables to estimate residents' marginal willingness to pay for improvements in SWM. In contrast, aesthetic improvement was treated as a dummy variable. Alternative-specific constants (ASCs) were incorporated as random parameters to capture unobserved preference heterogeneity, while interaction terms were modeled as fixed effects. To mitigate potential bias from attribute non-attendance (ANA), where respondents disregard certain attributes—self-reported ANA data were incorporated by constraining coefficients of ignored attributes to zero during estimation. Finally, the dataset was analyzed both as a pooled sample and stratified by city to evaluate overarching trends and location preferences.

3.2.1 Preference for SWM

The regression outcomes for the foundational Mixed Logit (MXL) model are displayed in Table 3.2, while the results adjusted for attribute non-attendance (ANA) are presented in Table 3.3. Around 28% of participants acknowledged overlooking at least one attribute when evaluating scenarios. According to the MXL model results for Finland and Norway (Table 3.2), residents expressed clear support for enhanced SWM strategies. They demonstrated a strong and increasing preference for measures offering higher levels of flood risk reduction (25%, 50%, and 75%). A comparable pattern emerged for runoff reduction, where approval rose from 25% to 50% reduction levels but slightly declined at the 75% level. This dip at the highest reduction tier is examined further in Section 3.3. Respondents were also positive about SWM measures that can improve the aesthetics of their private properties and the community, but to a lesser extent. Unsurprisingly, they preferred SWM measures with lower investment costs and less frequent maintenance requirements.

The results for the Finland and Norway datasets show the same trend when analyzed separately. However, there is a key difference between the two countries: Norwegians placed a lower value aesthetic improvement (not statistically significant) compared to Finns ($p < 0.05$). Additionally, the ASC of 1.20 indicates a stronger general preference for SWM alternatives over the status quo in Norway, compared to the results in Finland.

Although property ownership was initially thought to influence preferences, preliminary analysis revealed no significant difference between homeowners and renters. Consequently, the full dataset was used to ensure robust and comprehensive results, confirming the questionnaire's effectiveness for both groups. To further investigate any potential effect, ownership status was later included as an interaction term in the model, with those results discussed in the following section.

Table 3.2 Mixed logit (MXL) model regression results by country

Attributes	Finland (n=1013)		Norway (n=1000)		Both (n=2013)	
	Mean	Standard deviation	Mean	Standard deviation	Mean	Standard deviation
Price	-0.00*** (-0.00)	0.00*** (0.00)	-0.00*** (-0.00)	0.00*** (0.00)	-0.00*** (-0.00)	0.00*** (0.00)
-25% risk of damage	0.52*** (-0.08)	0.01 (0.48)	0.17** (-0.07)	0.44*** (0.19)	0.3*** (-0.05)	0.28** (0.14)
-50% risk of damage	0.70*** (-0.08)	0.31* (0.19)	0.21*** (-0.08)	0.37** (0.17)	0.43*** (-0.05)	0.19 (0.16)
-75% risk of damage	0.81*** (-0.08)	0.44*** (0.15)	0.27*** (-0.08)	0.61*** (0.14)	0.49*** (-0.05)	0.61*** (0.09)
-25% run-off	0.27*** (-0.06)	0.02 (0.17)	0.14** (-0.06)	0.01 (0.19)	0.20*** (-0.04)	0.08 (0.09)
-50% run-off	0.62*** (-0.07)	0.02 (0.18)	0.44*** (-0.07)	0.11 (0.26)	0.51*** (-0.05)	0.07 (0.11)
-75% run-off	0.53*** (-0.09)	0.01 (0.22)	0.38*** (-0.08)	0.14 (0.24)	0.46*** (-0.06)	0.15 (0.10)
Improve aesthetics	0.21** (-0.08)	0.67*** (0.22)	0.07 (-0.08)	0.91*** (0.17)	0.11** (-0.05)	0.40* (0.24)
Maintenance2 months	-0.61*** (-0.07)	0.64*** (0.14)	-0.45*** (-0.07)	0.61*** (0.14)	-0.52*** (-0.05)	0.50*** (0.10)
Maintenance6 months	-0.27*** (-0.06)	0.02 (0.13)	-0.38*** (-0.06)	0.02 (0.19)	-0.34*** (-0.04)	0.08 (0.07)
Maintenance 1 year	-0.14** (-0.07)	0.03 (0.22)	-0.16** (-0.07)	0.30 (0.21)	-0.18*** (-0.05)	0.04 (0.09)
ASC	1.12*** (-0.18)	3.81*** (0.19)	1.20*** (-0.14)	2.76*** (0.13)	1.10*** (-0.11)	3.06*** (0.10)
Observations	18,234	18234	18000	18000	36,234	36,234

^a The coefficients represent the means of the random distributions, except for the status quo, which is treated as a fixed coefficient. ASC refers to the alternative specific constant. Standard errors are shown in brackets. Significant coefficients are indicated with ***p < 0.01, **p < 0.05, *p < 0.1.

Table 3.3 Mixed logit (MXL) model corrected for attribute-non-attendance (ANA)

Attributes	Finland		Norway		Both	
	Mean	Standard deviation	Mean	Standard deviation	Mean	Standard deviation
Price	-0.00 *** (-0.00)	0.00*** (-0.00)	-0.00*** (-0.00)	0.00*** (0.00)	-0.00*** (-0.00)	0.00*** (0.00)
-25% risk of damage	0.50*** (-0.08)	0.01 (0.48)	0.17 ** (-0.07)	0.45*** (0.17)	0.33*** (-0.06)	0.19 (0.25)
-50% risk of damage	0.67 *** (-0.08)	0.31 * (0.19)	0.24 *** (-0.08)	0.36* (0.19)	0.41*** (-0.06)	0.24 (0.17)
-75% risk of damage	0.78 *** (-0.08)	0.44 *** (0.15)	0.29 *** (-0.07)	0.60 *** (0.14)	0.47*** (-0.06)	0.58*** (0.11)
-25% run-off	0.27 *** (-0.06)	0.02 (0.17)	0.18 ** (-0.06)	0.00 (0.16)	0.21*** (-0.05)	0.04 (0.10)
-50% run-off	0.59 *** (-0.07)	0.02 (0.18)	0.40 *** (-0.08)	0.07 (0.27)	0.42*** (-0.06)	0.06 (0.15)
-75% run-off	0.49 *** (-0.08)	0.01 (0.22)	0.40*** (-0.08)	0.07 (0.49)	0.40*** (-0.07)	0.07 (0.11)
Improve aesthetics	0.26 *** (-0.08)	0.67 *** (0.22)	0.15* (-0.08)	0.75 *** (0.19)	0.17*** (-0.06)	0.06 (0.22)
Maintenance2months	-0.56 *** (-0.07)	0.64 *** (0.14)	-0.35*** (-0.07)	0.49*** (0.16)	-0.46*** (-0.05)	0.22 (0.21)
Maintenance6months	-0.24*** (-0.06)	0.02 (0.13)	-0.33 *** (-0.06)	0.02 (0.20)	-0.31*** (-0.05)	0.01 (0.09)
Maintenance 1 year	-0.12 * (-0.07)	0.03 (0.22)	-0.14*** (-0.07)	0.16 (0.27)	-0.16*** (-0.05)	0.12 (0.11)
ASC	1.07*** (-0.17)	3.81 *** (0.19)	1.02 *** (-0.14)	2.76 *** (0.13)	1.06*** (-0.12)	2.90*** (0.11)
Observations	18,234	18,234	18,000	18,000	26,766	26,766

^a The coefficients represent the means of the random distributions, except for the status quo, which is treated as a fixed coefficient. ASC refers to the alternative specific constant. Standard errors are shown in brackets. Significant coefficients are indicated with ***p < 0.01, **p < 0.05, *p < 0.1.

3.2.2 Willingness to Pay

Table 3.4 shows results on the WTP for the SWM measures with different attributes in Finland and Norway. WTP is derived from the regression coefficients and expresses how much more or less

respondents are willing to pay to improve the SWM strategies. Findings are presented in Euro, providing insights into the relative significance given to the combinations and changes in various attributes by respondents.

Key findings reveal that WTP rises with greater reductions in property damage risk and runoff. Finns place a higher value on risk reduction (up to €4,820 for 75%), while Norwegians show a stronger preference for runoff reduction (up to €3,550 for 50%). Aesthetic improvements are valued more in Finland (€1,257) than Norway (€615). Both populations are averse to maintenance requirements, with Norwegians showing a stronger dislike, especially for lower maintenance. The positive ASC (Alternative Specific Constant) confirms a general preference for new SWM strategies over the status quo in both countries.

Table 3.4 Willingness to pay for stormwater management measures

Attributes	WTP (Euro)/ per household (one-time investment)	
	Finland	Norway
-25% risk of damage	3083	1350
-50% risk of damage	4209	1690
-75% risk of damage	4820	2130
-25% run-off	1592	1140
-50% run-off	3736	3550
-75% run-off	3143	3050
Improve aesthetics	1257	615
Maintenance 2 months	-3677	-3590
Maintenance 6 months	-1629	-3060
Maintenance 1 year	-838	-1270

3.2.3 Preference Heterogeneity

We found that preference heterogeneity among residents exists for four attributes (price, aesthetics, ASC and risk reduction 75%), based on the value of the standard deviation (If SD positive, the heterogeneity exists) (Table 3.2). To understand which factors influence residents’ preferences for SWM measures, we interacted the attributes of investment cost (price), improved aesthetics, and ASC with variables with the following variables: age, income, education, whether they had experienced floods, water quality in the local community, market value of the property, the amount of willingness to invest, whether they owned or rented their residence, and whether they had a garden or outdoor area. We did not include the attributes reduction 75% risk in the interaction analysis. This is because flood risk reduction was consistently valued positively across most respondents, making it less informative for explaining socio-demographic differences. Almost all the results with interaction terms were significant.

As shown in Table 3.5, the interaction terms for age, income, flood experience, property market value, neighborhood flood occurrence, and direct willingness to invest were statistically significant in both countries. Conversely, homeownership did not significantly influence price sensitivity or the preference for new SWM strategies over the status quo. The analysis further indicates that older respondents were less supportive of investing in SWM, while those with higher incomes, more education, prior flood experience, and higher-value properties showed a stronger preference for such investments.

Table 3.5 Mixed logit model with interaction terms

Attributes	Finland		Norway		Both	
	Mean	Standard deviation	Mean	Standard deviation	Mean	Standard deviation
ASC	1.12*** (-0.18)	3.81*** (0.19)	1.02*** (-0.14)	2.72*** (0.13)	1.10*** (-0.11)	3.06*** (0.10)
Price	-0.00*** (-0.00)	0.00*** (0.00)	-0.00*** (-0.00)	0.00*** (0.00)	-0.00*** (-0.00)	0.00*** (0.00)
Improve aesthetics	0.21** (-0.08)	0.67*** (0.22)	0.15* (-0.08)	0.75*** (0.19)	0.11** (-0.05)	0.40* (0.23)
Age*ASC	-0.05*** (-0.01)	--	-0.06*** (-0.01)	--	-0.05*** (-0.01)	--
Income*ASC	0.12*** (-0.03)		0.10*** (-0.02)		0.09*** (-0.02)	
Education*ASC	-0.01 (-0.01)		0.47*** (-0.10)		0.39*** (-0.07)	
Experience floods*ASC	0.00** (-0.00)		0.17*** (-0.06)		0.20*** (-0.05)	
Neighborhood happened floods*ASC	0.18*** (-0.06)		0.27*** (-0.05)		0.18*** (-0.04)	
Water quality*ASC	-0.04 (-0.21)		-0.37** (-0.15)		-0.21* (-0.11)	
Market*ASC	0.25** (-0.11)		0.31*** (-0.08)		0.19*** (-0.06)	
WTP*ASC	0.00*** (-0.00)		0.00*** (-0.00)		0.00*** (-0.00)	
Gender* price	-0.00 (-0.00)		-0.00 (-0.00)		0.00** (-0.00)	
Age*price	-0.00*** (-0.00)		-0.00** (-0.00)		-0.00*** (-0.00)	
Experience floods*price	0.00** (-0.00)		0.00 (-0.00)		0.00** (-0.00)	
Neighbourhood happened floods *price	0.00** (-0.00)		0.00 (-0.00)		0.00*** (-0.00)	
Own * price	0.00 (-0.00)		0.00 (-0.00)		0.00* (-0.00)	

Garden*price	-0.00 (-0.00)	0.00 (-0.00)	0.00* (-0.00)
WTP*price	0.00*** (-0.00)	0.00 (-0.00)	0.00*** (-0.00)
Own*aesthetics	0.01 (-0.01)	-0.06 (-0.17)	0.00* (-0.00)
Observations	18234	18000	36234

^a The coefficients represent the means of the random distributions, except for the status quo, which is treated as a fixed coefficient. ASC refers to the alternative specific constant. Standard errors are shown in brackets. Significant coefficients are indicated with ***p < 0.01, **p < 0.05, *p < 0.1.

3.3 Results from LCM

A Latent Class Model (LCM) was employed to explore the heterogeneity in preferences, specifically the observed variation in willingness to pay for increasing runoff reduction from 50% to 75%. This model segments respondents into distinct classes based on their choice patterns (Nylund et al., 2007). To identify the best-fitting model, versions with two and three classes were compared using the AIC, CAIC, and BIC criteria, which balance model fit against complexity. The three-class solution was selected as optimal. Subsequently, interaction terms for age, income, gender, and education were incorporated. The final model retained only statistically significant variables. The results for the LCM, both with and without these interaction terms, are presented in Table 3.6.

The Latent Class Model segmented Finnish respondents into three distinct groups based on their preferences. The majority (70%), classified as Class 1, were typically younger, high-income individuals with lower education levels and a slightly higher proportion of females; this segment demonstrated a positive preference for flood risk and runoff reduction, a moderate valuation of aesthetics, and an aversion to frequent maintenance. A smaller segment, Class 2 (17.5%), comprised older, high-income respondents with lower education who were generally unsupportive of stormwater management measures, showing negative preferences for risk and runoff reduction, though they valued aesthetic improvements and shorter, two-month maintenance intervals. Finally, Class 3 (12.8%), consisting of older, lower-income, highly-educated, predominantly male respondents, most closely mirrored general supportive preferences, showing positive attitudes toward risk reduction, runoff reduction, and aesthetic benefits, while also disliking maintenance requirements.

Additionally, analysis of the Norwegian dataset revealed three primary respondent segments. The vast majority (76%), designated as Class 3, were younger, higher-income males who strongly favored strategies for risk and runoff reduction but had little interest in aesthetics and a clear aversion to maintenance. In contrast, a much smaller group, Class 1 (9.1%), consisted of older, lower-income, highly-educated females. While generally supportive of stormwater management initiatives, they were specifically opposed to a 50% runoff reduction target and frequent maintenance. Finally, Class 2 (15.4%) was composed of older, higher-income females with lower education levels. This segment was unsupportive of a 50% damage reduction goal but held positive preferences for runoff reduction.

Analysis of the combined dataset identified three distinct preference classes. The dominant segment, Class 3 (72.5%), is characterized by younger, higher-income, highly-educated males who support stormwater management (SWM) measures for damage reduction, runoff reduction, and aesthetic improvement, but are opposed to increased maintenance. Class 2 (16.5%) consists of older, higher-income females with lower education levels. This group demonstrates conditional support, favoring

damage and runoff reduction only at specific levels and preferring shorter maintenance intervals, yet overall is generally unsupportive of SWM initiatives. Class 1 (11.0%), comprising older, lower-income, highly-educated males, aligns with general SWM preferences by supporting damage and runoff reduction, but shares the common negative view toward maintenance.

In summary, the dominant preference groups in both countries are younger, high-income individuals who prioritize practical SWM benefits like damage and runoff control. While showing moderate interest in aesthetics, these groups consistently oppose frequent maintenance. The influence of gender and education on preferences was more complex and varied between the two countries, indicating that these factors do not produce consistent trends across different cultural contexts.

Table 3.6 Latent class model results with and without interaction terms

Variable	Finland			Norway			Both		
	Class 1	Class 2	Class 3	Class 1	Class 2	Class 3	Class 1	Class 2	Class 3
	(69.7%)	(17.5%)	(12.8%)	(9.1%)	(15.4%)	(75.6%)	(11.0%)	(16.5%)	(72.5%)
Price	-0.000	0.000	-0.001	-0.001	-0.000	-0.000	-0.001	-0.000	-0.000
-25% risk of damage	0.353	-0.935	0.654	0.183	3.530	0.109	0.512	0.540	0.221
-50% risk of damage	0.504	-0.492	1.519	1.312	-37.65	0.127	1.387	-0.358	0.301
-75% risk of damage	0.644	-1.801	1.404	0.687	4.030	0.198	1.106	0.550	0.402
-25% run-off	0.218	-1.592	0.326	1.108	1.139	0.052	0.666	0.256	0.132
-50% run-off	0.435	-0.344	0.725	-0.157	1.573	0.277	0.434	0.185	0.344
-75% run-off	0.407	-0.637	0.703	0.413	-1.607	0.191	0.534	-0.163	0.289
Improve aesthetics	0.095	0.154	0.509	0.828	1.738	0.072	0.689	0.111	0.082
Maintenance 2 months	-0.496	0.446	-1.320	-2.609	0.933	-0.297	-1.741	0.163	-0.391
Maintenance 6 months	-0.196	-0.223	-0.758	-0.846	2.363	-0.296	-0.724	0.271	-0.248
Maintenance 1 year	-0.196	-18.587	-0.309	-1.495	2.304	-0.168	-0.757	-0.276	-0.184
ASC	1.427	-3.697	0.265	1.363	-9.804	1.332	0.610	-4.589	1.378
Interaction terms									
Age	-0.027	0.025	0.000	0.030	0.062	0.000	0.030	0.056	0.000
Income	0.001	0.004	0.000	-0.002	0.010	0.000	-0.001	0.006	0.000
Gender	0.285	0.295	0.000	0.341	0.083	0.000	-0.022	0.010	0.000
Education	-0.007	-0.001	0.000	0.006	-0.018	0.000	0.002	-0.004	0.000
LLF	-5119.7			-5426.5			-10607.1		
CAIC	10587.9			11200.9			21592.9		
BIC	10543.9			11156.9			21548.9		

3.4 Additional Survey Findings

In the questionnaire, we included questions that directly asked respondents which factors they prioritize when considering SWM. Same as the priority from MXL model, both Finnish and Norwegian residents ranked flood risk reduction to their property as the top priority but considered low maintenance (time

requirements) the second most important factor. This suggests that residents take into account the cost or timing of SWM when maintenance is required. After that, they consider reducing runoff and improving water quality as important factors when deciding which SWM measure to invest in on their private property.

Another question asked to respondents was which SWM measures they had in mind to install on their properties when completing the choice sets in the hypothetical scenario (Table 3.7). Most respondents (32%) in both countries indicated permeable surface as their first choice. Then, redirecting the drainpipe (30%) and rain garden (26%) were also considered important options in both countries. Then followed by sump bump (19%) and green roof (17%), green wall (16%), green ditch (13%), stormwater chamber (10%). In both Finland and Norway, the preference for SWM followed the same trend: they preferred permeable pavement and redirecting the drainpipe as their top two SWM options, which showed the balanced preference of green and grey infrastructure.

Additionally, we analyzed the demographic background of respondents for this question and found consistent patterns across both datasets. In both Finland and Norway, residents aged 30-40, with incomes between €1500-€3000 and holding a second degree, are more likely to choose permeable pavement. For rain gardens, the primary age groups are 20-30 and 30-40. Finally, for redirecting the drainpipe, the key demographic includes individuals aged 50-60 and those over 60. Lastly, we asked respondents about their perceptions of how decision-makers and authorities would respond to the survey results. In both Finland and Norway, residents exhibited a neutral attitude toward the likelihood of authorities taking action based on the survey's findings. This statement is crucial for enhancing the study's consequentiality, meaning respondents perceive a real possibility that their answers could influence decision-making. This belief should motivate them to provide more truthful responses (Johnston et al., 2017).

Table 3.7 Stormwater management that citizen had in mind to install on their properties

Stormwater management strategies	Finland			Norway		
	General (1013)	Own (500/1013)	Rented (506/1013)	General (1000)	Own (691/1000)	Rented (293/1013)
Permeable surface	0.33	16.19	16.78	0.31	20.8	9.8
Rain garden	0.19	8.39	9.97	0.26	16.1	8.9
Green ditch	0.09	5.03	4.15	0.22	14.6	7.3
Green wall	0.10	3.95	5.53	0.17	11.4	5.1
Stormwater chamber	0.09	3.95	5.33	0.11	7.6	3.6
Sump pump	0.22	9.87	11.84	0.15	10.5	4.5
Rain tank	0.07	3.06	4.05	0.18	11.9	5.9
Redirecting the drainpipe	0.35	17.97	17.17	0.25	18.9	6.1
Green roof	0.24	13.23	11.25	0.09	6.5	2.1

3.5 Workshop Findings

While Sections 3.1-3.4 report survey-based results, this section presents complementary qualitative findings from the resident workshop. Twelve people participated in the workshop, including local

residents and a small number of municipal employees. The group was motivated, engaged with the theme, and recognized that climate change has significant impacts on everyday life.

The key results from their discussions are summarized below:

Preferences for Green and Practical Yards: Participants favored yards with abundant vegetation and permeable surfaces, valuing them both for aesthetics and for their ability to reduce stormwater runoff and provide shade. Yards dominated by concrete or flat lawns were seen as less attractive and less resilient. Residents also discussed compromises they had made in their own yards, such as preserving views or adapting to limited space.

Climate Risks and Seasonal Challenges: Rain and stormwater were identified as the most pressing risks, linked to impervious surfaces, clogged gutters, and insufficient water retention. Participants also pointed to winter hazards (slippery surfaces, snow load), summer challenges (lawn burn, overheating), and storm-related damage. These risks were seen as increasingly relevant to household maintenance and comfort.

Solutions and Adaptation Ideas: Nature-based stormwater solutions were the most popular. Residents proposed vegetated depressions, permeable pavements, infiltration areas, and, where space is limited, vertical greenery such as walls or roofs. They emphasized the role of diverse and drought-resistant planting in managing both heat and water risks, while enhancing biodiversity. Simple measures such as redirecting stormwater into yards instead of streets were also highlighted.

Need for Support and Guidance: Participants stressed that while they are willing to act, they require clear guidance, model examples, and financial support. Practical demonstrations, advice on how to delay and direct stormwater, and visible city-led initiatives were considered essential. Financing was mentioned as a barrier, reinforcing the survey finding that affordability is central to uptake.

Overall, the workshop confirmed that residents recognize stormwater risks, are able to identify feasible solutions, and value municipal support in making action possible. The discussions reinforced survey findings on the importance of property protection, runoff management, aesthetics, and low-maintenance designs, while adding a practical perspective on the role of guidance, awareness, and co-creation in encouraging household-level adaptation.

4.0 RECOMMENDATIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

This section outlines in detail the recommendations derived from the survey findings based on the analysis of citizens' responses to stormwater management (SWM) as well the results from resident workshop in Lappeenranta (Finland). Together, these findings highlight how willingness to pay (WTP), stated preferences, and household-level experiences can inform the development of stormwater management (SWM) policies and practices in Finland and Norway. The recommendations are organized into six interrelated directions, each supported by evidence that guides effective, inclusive, and citizen-oriented decision-making.

4.1 Property and Water Protection

Flood risk reduction was the strongest and most consistent driver of citizen support in both Finland and Norway. The mixed logit model results confirmed significant positive coefficients for reductions in property risk, while WTP estimates indicated that Finnish households were ready to invest up to €4,820 per household for a 75% risk reduction of damage. Norwegian respondents, while valuing property protection, demonstrated strong concern for runoff reduction, valuing a 50% reduction at €3,550 per household.

- **Property Protection:** SWM strategies must focus on reducing the likelihood of direct household damage, particularly in flood-prone Finnish urban areas. Concrete messaging on how measures such as permeable pavements or redirected drainpipes prevent flooding will strengthen public support.
- **Runoff Management:** In Norway, SWM designs should highlight their capacity to reduce polluted runoff entering rivers and lakes, directly linking measures to healthier ecosystems.
- **Combined Framing:** Presenting SWM as simultaneously reducing property risks and improving water quality ensures citizens see multiple benefits, strengthening willingness to invest.
- **Yard-Scale Measures:** Residents also stressed runoff and drainage risks at the household scale, pointing to clogged gutters, surface runoff, and moisture damage, and proposed practical actions such as permeable yards, redirecting stormwater into gardens, and green depressions.

4.2 Enhance Aesthetic Value

While aesthetics ranked below property protection and runoff management, the study revealed that aesthetic improvements significantly shaped citizen preferences, especially in Finland. The WTP for enhanced aesthetics reached €1,257 in Finland and €615 in Norway. Although secondary, these figures show that aesthetics remain a valued attribute that can make the difference between acceptance and reluctance.

- **Green Infrastructure Integration:** Incorporating rain gardens, green roofs, and vegetated ditches into SWM adds environmental and visual value. These elements make SWM more acceptable in densely populated urban areas.
- **Neighborhood Wellbeing:** Respondents linked visual quality improvements to better mental health, increased recreational opportunities, and higher property values.
- **Vegetation Design:** Workshop discussions highlighted preference for layered, diverse, and drought-tolerant vegetation that not only improves aesthetics but also provides shade, reduces heat, and manages stormwater effectively.
- **Policy Direction:** Municipalities should avoid treating aesthetics as a marginal benefit. Instead, they should integrate greenery and design features into every major SWM project to maximize citizen acceptance.

4.3 Reduce Maintenance Burdens

The findings clearly showed that maintenance frequency is a decisive factor. Respondents displayed a particularly strong aversion, with a negative WTP of - €3,677 in Finland and - €3,590 in Norway for measures requiring bi-monthly maintenance. Minimal upkeep signaling that long-term viability depends on reducing maintenance burdens.

- **Low-Maintenance Designs:** Favor SWM options that require no more than annual or bi-annual upkeep, such as permeable pavements or retention tanks.
- **Clear Guidance:** Residents emphasized the need for simple, model solutions and step-by-step instructions to make low-maintenance designs practical at the household level.
- **Municipal Support:** Municipalities should consider offering shared maintenance services, ensuring installations remain effective while reducing burdens on individual households.
- **Realistic Communication:** Authorities must provide honest information on upkeep needs to prevent overestimation of effort, which could deter adoption.
- **Policy Example:** Community-level contracts for green roof upkeep or municipal inspection programs could significantly improve citizen confidence.

4.4 Tailor to Citizen Groups

The heterogeneity analysis revealed three citizen groups with distinct priorities: Risk Reducers, Environmentalists, and Cost-Sensitive Citizens. Each requires tailored strategies.

- **Risk Reducers:** This majority group, often older and of moderate income, focused on property protection. Messages should emphasize safety, reduced flooding, and property value preservation.
- **Environmentalists:** Younger, highly educated, and higher-income respondents strongly valued aesthetics and runoff reduction. Highlighting ecological and recreational benefits can mobilize this group.
- **Cost-Sensitive Citizens:** With low WTP, this group needs affordable, low-maintenance options. Subsidies and simple measures like redirecting drainpipes should be promoted here.
- **Practical Contexts:** Workshop discussions added that even motivated residents face constraints such as small yard size or competing priorities, requiring flexible designs like green walls, compact infiltration basins, or shared spaces.
- **Segmented Communication:** Outreach should be differentiated. For example, public campaigns for Environmentalists might stress biodiversity benefits, while Risk Reducers may respond better to flood risk maps and cost-saving guarantees.

4.5 Ensure Equity in Access

The results show that WTP correlates with income, education, and property value, raising risks of inequity. Without corrective measures, SWM adoption may disproportionately benefit wealthier households, leaving low-income and elderly residents behind.

- **Progressive Financing Models:** Contributions should scale according to income or property value to ensure fairness.
- **Targeted Subsidies:** Provide grants or fee reductions for households with limited financial capacity, particularly elderly citizens or renters.
- **Neighborhood-Level Interventions:** In rental-heavy urban districts, municipalities should invest directly in communal SWM, such as permeable pavements for streets or communal gardens.

- **Affordability Support:** Residents also flagged cost as a bottleneck and highlighted the importance of subsidies, co-funding schemes, or demonstration projects to make SWM feasible for all households.
- **Equitable Benefits:** Policies must guarantee that all residents, regardless of income or ownership, benefit from reduced flood risk and improved water quality.

4.6 Build Transparency and Trust

Respondents expressed neutral expectations about whether authorities would act on survey findings. This signals a potential trust gap that could undermine citizens' willingness to participate.

- **Transparency:** Regularly communicate how citizen input informs municipal SWM strategies.
- **Demonstration Projects:** Implement visible local pilots, such as rain gardens or permeable parking lots, to provide proof of effectiveness.
- **Outcome Reporting:** Publish accessible reports showing measurable reductions in flood risk and runoff pollution.
- **Citizen Engagement:** Develop participatory planning forums and digital feedback channels to strengthen accountability and ownership.
- **Practical Examples:** Residents called for model yards and visible examples to make solutions tangible and turn awareness into action.

In summary, the analysis from the survey and workshop demonstrates that citizens in Finland and Norway are willing to share responsibility for SWM, provided measures are effective, affordable, and equitable. Policies must focus on reducing flood risk, improving water quality, enhancing aesthetics, minimizing maintenance burdens, and ensuring fairness. Tailored communication and transparent practices will help authorities build long-term trust and secure broad support for climate adaptation.

By acting on these six directions, policymakers can align technical solutions with citizen priorities, strengthen resilience against climate impacts, and build inclusive and trusted pathways toward sustainable urban living.

5.0 CONCLUSIONS

5.1 Key Messages

Citizens are willing to pay for effective SWM. The study revealed a high willingness to pay (WTP) for measures that reduce flood risk and stormwater runoff, though the relative emphasis differs between countries. Finnish households were willing to pay up to €4,820 for a 75% reduction in flood risk damage, while Norwegian households showed strong support for runoff reduction, with WTP up to €3,550 for a 50% reduction. These figures demonstrate strong public commitment to climate resilience when benefits are clear and tangible. Discussions with residents confirmed that these priorities are also recognized at the household level, where practical risks such as runoff, clogged gutters, and moisture damage are most visible.

Flood risk reduction is the top priority. Across both countries, the most valued outcome was reducing the likelihood of property damage. Citizens view SWM first and foremost as a way to protect their homes and families from increasing climate risks. At the yard scale, residents highlighted the same concerns, pointing to solutions such as permeable surfaces and redirected drainpipes.

Runoff reduction and water quality are crucial, especially in Norway. Norwegian respondents emphasized environmental co-benefits such as reducing pollution and improving water quality. In Finland, these factors were also valued but played a secondary role to property protection. Residents linked runoff control with visible yard-level measures such as green depressions and rain gardens.

Aesthetic improvements matter, especially in Finland. Although not the primary driver, aesthetic benefits—such as greener neighborhoods, rain gardens, and green roofs—were positively valued, with higher WTP in Finland than Norway. These features can boost community acceptance and quality of life. Residents also stressed the role of layered, drought-tolerant vegetation that combines beauty with shade, biodiversity, and water retention.

Maintenance requirements are a critical barrier. Frequent maintenance reduced WTP significantly. Low-maintenance designs and municipal maintenance support are therefore essential to citizen acceptance and long-term viability. Residents echoed this, noting that time, cost, and upkeep burden are major constraints unless supported by clear model solutions and guidance.

Preferences are diverse and shaped by socio-economic factors. The latent class analysis identified three distinct groups: Risk Reducers, Environmentalists, and Cost-Sensitive Citizens. Age, income, education, flood experience, and property value strongly influenced WTP and preferences. Workshop discussions confirmed that constraints such as limited yard size or competing household priorities also shape what households can realistically adopt.

Equity and inclusiveness must be prioritized. Wealthier and better-educated households were more supportive, while older and low-income groups were less so. Without subsidies or community-level investments, vulnerable citizens risk being left behind. Participants emphasized that affordability is key and called for municipal subsidies, shared financing, and demonstration projects to lower barriers.

Trust in authorities remains limited. Respondents expressed neutral expectations about whether municipalities would act on their input. Building transparency and demonstrating responsiveness will be key to strengthening legitimacy. Residents reinforced this by calling for visible demonstration yards, model solutions, and clear communication to translate awareness into action.

Together, these messages make clear that successful SWM strategies must combine technical effectiveness with social acceptability, equity, and transparency.

5.2 Final Note

The evidence gathered through this DCE solution offers a unique opportunity for policymakers. It provides not just abstract economic valuations but concrete guidance on how to design SWM systems that citizens are willing to adopt and finance. The integration of workshop perspectives further illustrates how survey findings translate into everyday household experiences, underscoring the importance of combining quantitative and qualitative methods in future adaptation planning. The challenge for governments and municipalities now lies in translating these insights into actionable, inclusive, and transparent policies that secure citizen buy-in, reduce urban flooding risks, and improve the resilience of the living environment for present and future generations. Key partners in Finland (City of Lappeenranta) and Norway (Municipality of Gjøvik) will continue to engage local stakeholders and citizens in this process, further developing co-created stormwater management solutions. This work will be carried forward within the BALTFLOOD Project (March 2025 - February 2028), supported by Interreg, to ensure that evidence-based, citizen-driven approaches inform regional adaptation strategies.

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ANNEX

1. Questionnaire

Discrete Choice Experiment to be distributed in Finland and Norway

Dear survey participant,

Thank you for taking the time to respond to our survey. Your participation will help us inform policy discussions on improving the management of stormwater in **[Norway/Finland]**.

This survey is being carried out by the **[city of Lappeenranta/the Municipality of Gjovik]** and the University of Antwerp as part of the project '*TransformAr - Accelerating and upscaling transformational adaptation in Europe: demonstration of water-related innovation packages*', and is funded by the European Union within the Horizon 2020 Programme.

The results of this study will be considered in upcoming local, national and European policy discussions and developments related to urban stormwater management.

This survey will take approximately 15 minutes, with certain sections containing text and questions which will require your concentration. There are no right or wrong answers and all responses are strictly confidential and anonymous.

None of your responses will be attributed to you personally. Data collected in the survey will be managed in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR).

Thank you!

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon H2020 innovation action programme under grant agreement 101036683.

SECTION 1 – YOU AND YOUR HOUSEHOLD

1. I live in a: [ONE ANSWER]

Detached house

- Semi-detached house
- Terraced house
- Apartment
- Other

1.2 Do you own or rent your primary residence? [ONE ANSWER]

- I own it
- I rent it
- Prefer not to say

1.3 How many people live in your household (including yourself)? [ONE ANSWER]

- 1
- 2

- 3
- 4
- More than 4

I live in a: [ONE ANSWER]

Detached house

- Semi-detached house
- Terraced house
- Apartment
- Other

1.4 Does your primary residence have a garden or outdoor area? [ONE ANSWER]

- Yes
- No

1.5 How far away from your home is your nearest public green space area (e.g. park, playing field, woodland, or other green space)? [ONE ANSWER]

- <5 minute walk
- Within 5-10 minute walk
- >10 minute walk

1.6 What is the current market value of your primary residence? [ONE ANSWER]

- <100 000 Eur / 1 mil KR
- 100 – 300 000 Eur / 1 – 3 mil KR
- 300 – 500 000 Eur / 3 – 5 mil KR
- 500 – 800 000 Eur / 5 – 8 mil KR
- >800 000 Eur / >8 mil KR
- I don't know
- Prefer not to say

1.7 When was your place of residence constructed? [ONE ANSWER]

- Before 1950
- 1950-1980
- 1980-2000
- 2000-2010
- After 2010
- I don't know

SECTION 2 – YOUR LOCAL COMMUNITY AND IMPACTS OF CLIMATE CHANGE

2.1 Has your property been affected by floods? [ONE ANSWER]

- Once to several times a year
- Once a year
- Every 1-3 years
- Every 3-5 years
- Every 5-10 years
- Less than once a decade
- Never
- I don't know

- Other

2.2 Is your neighbourhood (neighbouring streets) affected by floods? [ONE ANSWER]

- Once to several times a year
- Once a year
- Every 1-3 years
- Every 3-5 years
- Every 5-10 years
- Less than once a decade
- Never
- I don't know
- Other

2.3 How would you rate the water quality in your local community (in streams, rivers, lakes)? [ONE ANSWER]

- **1 - Bad**
- **2 - Poor**
- **3 - Moderate,**
- **4 - Good**
- **5 - High**
- I don't know

2.4 What are, in your opinion, the three biggest threats to water quality in your community in the list below? You do not have to choose any if you think there are no threats in your community (option M). [MIN 0 – MAX 3 ANSWERS POSSIBLE]

A. Agricultural pollution
B. Aquaculture and commercial fishing
C. Recreational fishing and angling
D. Flooding
E. Industrial pollution
F. Algal blooms
G. Plastics and litter
H. Temperature Change
I. Tourism
J. Urban development (urban/domestic wastewater)
K. Draining of swamps
L. Something else
M. None of the above

2.5 In wintertime, has anyone you know experienced accidents or injuries as a result of ice covering surfaces in the past year? [ONE ANSWER]

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

2.6 If yes, do you think better water/snow management or prevention could have prevented the injury? [ONE ANSWER]

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

SECTION 3 – CLIMATE CHANGE AND STORMWATER MANAGEMENT

Extreme weather events are occurring more often due to the impacts of climate change. In the event of heavy rainfall, you may experience floods on your property, as the stormwater and drainage network will be overloaded. The reason for this overload is that the city's or municipality's network is not designed for the quantities of water that can occur during heavy rainfall events, such as Storm Hans which hit Scandinavian countries in August 2023.

Impact of Storm Hans in Norway, August 2023

To adapt to these impacts of climate change, and to relieve the water network, it is important that both the government and citizens take action. If stormwater management measures are implemented in your local community and your property, water will naturally go into the ground, and not flow into the drainage network at once. This reduces the risk of flooding, in addition to risks caused by winter rainfall, freezing temperatures and ice covering surfaces on your property, and as a result: a reduced risk of falls, injuries and accidents. Increased stormwater management will also improve water quality as a result of a reduction in run-off pollutants flowing into local water bodies.

3.1 Have you ever seen or heard of the below measures to deal with stormwater on private properties? You can choose more than one. [MULTIPLE ANSWERS POSSIBLE]

- Permeable surface (e.g. replace asphalt in driveway with gravel or paving stones)
- Rain garden
- Green ditch
- Green wall
- Green roof
- Stormwater chamber

- Sump pump
- Rain tank
- Redirecting the drainpipe
- None of the above

3.2 Have any of the below measures to manage stormwater been installed on your property (your own or rented)? [MULTIPLE ANSWERS]

- Permeable surface (e.g. replace asphalt in driveway with gravel or paving stones)
- Rain garden
- Green ditch
- Green wall
- Green roof
- Stormwater chamber
- Sump pump
- Rain tank
- Redirecting the drainpipe
- None of the above

3.3 If you *have* installed stormwater measures on your property, did it this/these measure(s) help reduce flood damage or reduce accidents because of ice covering surfaces? [ONE ANSWER]

- Yes
- No
- I don't know
- I haven't installed any stormwater measures on my property

3.4 [IF yes] Did you install the stormwater measure(s) on your property especially because of concerns of accidents from ice covering surfaces? [ONE ANSWER]

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

3.5 Do you think Nordic conditions (e.g. heavy snowfall and frost) increase the need for effective stormwater management? [ONE ANSWER]

- Yes
- No
- I don't know
-

SECTION 4 - DISCRETE CHOICE EXPERIMENT

HYPOTHETICAL SCENARIO:

Imagine the following hypothetical scenario: You are considering purchasing one of the below stormwater management measures for your private property to capture increased rainfall and stormwater. You own a detached 120 m² house with a garden.

In the following section, we will ask you to **choose your preferred stormwater management measures based on their costs and benefits below**. You will be asked afterwards which specific measures you had in mind. We will NOT specify the specific measure, however all the options do represent some indirectly.

You are also given the option to opt-out of the choice, and not implement a stormwater measure on your property. The prices provided are for a detached 120 m² house with a garden.

You will be given the option to choose 6 independent times. There are no right or wrong answers.

ASPECTS TO CONSIDER WHEN CHOOSING A STORMWATER MANAGEMENT MEASURE PRESENTED TO YOU:

Please read the explanation of the different characteristics of possible measures carefully before starting to choose between hypothetical scenarios presented to you!

		<u>Definition</u>	<u>Levels to choose from</u>
	Reduced risk of damage to the house	By installing effective stormwater management measures on your property, you reduce the risk of flooding and minimise potential damage caused by excessive rainfall compared to what may occur in its present condition.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 75 % less risk of damage - 50 % less risk of damage - 25 % less risk of damage No reduction in risk of damage (same as now)
	Reduced stormwater run-off and pollution	Stormwater runoff is the water that flows over the surface when it rains or when snow and ice melt. Instead of soaking into the ground, this water runs off over streets, parking lots, and rooftops, picking up pollutants (like oil, chemicals, sediments and debris). Effective stormwater management will reduce the stormwater runoff from your property, including pollutants, flowing into local water bodies, thus ensuring local water quality.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 75 % less run-off pollutants - 50 % less run-off pollutants - 25 % less run-off pollutants No reduction in run-off pollutants (same as now)
	Improved aesthetics of the property and community	The stormwater measure can beautify your property and the local community (or not).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Yes No (same as now)
	Frequency of maintenance required	The number of times you will have to take action to maintain the stormwater management measure each year.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Once every 2 months Once every 6 months Once a year Once every 5 years None (no new measure)
	Price (investment cost)	The price to pay to install the stormwater management measure on your property.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5000 KR/500 EUR 10 000 KR/1 000 EUR 20 000 KR/2 000 EUR 50 000 KR/5 000 EUR 100 000 KR/10 000 EUR 0 KR/0 EUR (no new measure)

	Reduced risk of damage to the house	Reduced stormwater run-off and pollution	Improvement of aesthetics of the property and community	Frequency of maintenance required	Price (investment cost)
A	 5000 KR				
B	 100 000 KR				
C	No new stormwater management measure				

SECTION 5 – POST-EXPERIMENTAL QUESTIONNAIRE

5.1 Were the choices clear to you?

- Yes
- No

5.2 Did you ignore any of the attributes when making your decision?

- Yes
- No

5.3 If yes, which one(s) did you ignore [MULTIPLE CHOICES ALLOWED]

- Reduced flood risk and damage to my house in case of flooding

- **Reduced run-off of pollutants** flowing into local water
- **Maintenance** (time requirements)
- **Improved aesthetics** of local neighbourhood
- **Investment cost**

5.4 When filling in the hypothetical choice scenarios, which stormwater management measure(s) did you have in mind to install on your private property? Please choose your preferred option.

[MULTIPLEONE ANSWERS]

- Permeable surface (e.g. replace asphalt in driveway with gravel or paving stones)
- Rain garden
- Green ditch
- Green wall
- Stormwater chamber
- Sump pump
- Rain tank
- Redirecting the drainpipe
- Green roof
- None of the above

5.5 If you were to install a stormwater management measure on your property, which of the following factors would you consider most? Please rank, from 1 (most important) to 5 (least important). **[RANKING FROM 1 TO 5]**

- **Reduced flood risk** and damage to my house in case of flooding
- Improved **water quality**
- **Maintenance** (time requirements)
- **Improved aesthetics** of local neighbourhood
- **Investment cost**

5.6 How much would you be willing to pay for a stormwater management measure on your property?

0----->10 000 euros

5.7 If you chose to not install a stormwater measure on one of the cards (option C), why? **[MULTIPLE CHOICES ALLOWED]**

- It was too expensive
- I do not have problems with flooding or accidents as a result of ice on my property
- I do not want to buy the measures proposed
- I do not know enough about stormwater management to be sure
- It is the government's responsibility
- Other

5.8 How likely is it, in your opinion, that what you reported in this survey and those of other consumers will be taken into account by policymakers and authorities in your country? Please select your answer on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1=not likely at all and 5=very likely.

1= not likely at all	2	3	4	5= very likely	6= I don't know
1	2	3	4	5	6

SECTION 6 - SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC QUESTIONS

6.1 What is your age? [ONE ANSWER]

- [Drop-down]
- Prefer not to say

6.2 What is your gender? [ONE ANSWER]

- F
- M
- Non-binary
- Prefer not to say

6.3 Which county do you live in (NO – 11 from drop-down menu)/which region do you live in (FI – 19 from drop-down menu)? _____

6.4 What is your highest level of education? [ONE ANSWER]

- Primary education
- Secondary education
- Technical and vocational post-secondary
- Bachelor
- Master
- PhD
- Prefer not to say

6.5 What is your household monthly net income (your income after taxes)? [ONE ANSWER]

Finland:

[1]	Less than € 500
[2]	Between € 501 and € 750
[3]	Between € 751 and € 1000
[4]	Between € 1001 and € 1250
[5]	Between € 1251 and € 1500
[6]	Between € 1501 and € 2000
[7]	Between € 2001 and € 2500
[8]	Between € 2501 and € 3000
[9]	Between € 3001 and € 3500
[10]	Between € 3501 and € 4000
[11]	Between € 4001 and € 4500
[12]	Between € 4501 and € 5000
[13]	Between € 5001 and € 5500
[14]	Between € 5501 and € 6000
[15]	Between € 6001 and € 7500
[16]	Between € 7501 and 12500
[17]	Over € 12500
[88]	I don't know
[99]	I prefer not to answer

Norway

[1]	Mindre enn 8000 kroner
-----	------------------------

[2]	Mellom 8001 og 12000 kroner
[3]	Mellom 12001 og 16000 kroner
[4]	Mellom 16001 og 20000 kroner
[5]	Mellom 20001 og 24000 kroner
[6]	Mellom 24001 og 32000 kroner
[7]	Mellom 32001 og 40000 kroner
[8]	Mellom 40001 og 48000 kroner
[9]	Mellom 48001 og 55000 kroner
[10]	Mellom 55001 og 63000 kroner
[11]	Mellom 63001 og 72000 kroner
[12]	Mellom 72001 og 80000 kroner
[13]	Mellom 80001 og 87000 kroner
[14]	Mellom 87001 og 95000 kroner
[15]	Mellom 95001 og 120000 kroner
[16]	Mellom 120001 og 200 000 kroner
[17]	Over 200 000 kroner
[88]	Jeg vet ikke
[99]	Jeg foretrekker ikke å svare

6.6 What is your main occupation? _____ [ONE ANSWER]

- Employed, full-time
- Employed, part-time
- Not employed
- Retired
- Disabled, not able to work
- Student
- I prefer not to say

TransformAr

www.transformar.eu

Climate change impacts are here and now. The impacts on people, prosperity and planet are already pervasive but unevenly distributed, as stated in the new EU Blueprint strategy (European Commission-EC, 2019). To reduce climate-related risks, the EC and the IPCC agree that transformational adaptation is essential. The TransformAr project aims to develop and demonstrate products and services to launch and accelerate large-scale and disruptive adaptive process for transformational adaptation in vulnerable regions and communities across Europe.

The 6 TransformAr lighthouse demonstrators face a common challenge: water-related risks and impacts of climate change. Based on existing successful initiatives, the project will develop, test and demonstrate solutions and pathways, integrated in Innovation Packages, in 6 territories.

Transformational pathways, including an integrated risk assessment approach are co-developed by means of 9 Transformational Adaptive Blocks. A set of 22 tested actionable adaptive solutions are tested and demonstrated, ranging from nature-based solutions, innovative technologies, financing, insurance and governance models, awareness and behavioral change solutions.

TransformAr

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